

Orthographic cues for quantity distinctions in L2

Elisabeth Zetterholm¹, Mechtild Tronnier²

¹ *Department of Language Education, Stockholm University, Sweden*

² *Centre for Languages and Literature, Lund University, Sweden*
elisabeth.zetterholm@isd.su.se, mechtild.tronnier@ling.lu.se

Abstract

Adult second language learners often learn both written and spoken language more or less simultaneously. The orthography of the world's languages is, however, not in a one-to-one relationship with the phonological and phonetic realisations of its words. Sometimes orthographic cues as a clue for learners can be found and taught. If not, the pronunciation of the word has to be learned from other cues than orthography. In Swedish, there is an important quantity distinction in stressed syllables, often signalled by single or double consonantal letters.

Minimal pairs with a quantity distinction shown in the orthography were used to study to what extent that might be a cue for second language learners when reading sentences in Swedish. We found a difference between speakers that can be correlated to the learner's first language. Obvious relationships between orthographic and phonological quantity patterns make it easier to use orthography as a cue for quantity distinction and pronunciation.

Introduction

Written texts, both in everyday life and in language learning classes, are often large parts of the input for second language (L2) learners. For reading skills learners have to be aware of the orthographic-phonemic relationship as well as differences between spoken and written language. In that way the alphabetic script is related to the phonemic structure of the language. Furthermore, words can be singled out by spaces in the written text. That is not as easily done in

spoken language. Spelling rules and the translation between letters and phonemes are of importance when learning to read and write. This is true for acquisition of both first (L1) and additional languages. In L1, spoken language comes first, but adult L2 learners often acquire both spoken and written language at the same time. L2 orthographic forms can affect both perception and production in L2, especially for learners in early stages (e.g. Bassetti 2008; Bassetti, Escudera & Hayes-Harb, 2015). They often decode similar grapheme with the same phoneme as in their L1.

The present study

Adult second language learners of Swedish with Albanian, Italian and Spanish as their L1 are recorded when reading prepared sentences with target words. Minimal pairs with a quantity contrast were used in order to study to what extent the orthography might be a cue for the learners' pronunciation in Swedish, or not. In all four languages alphabetic scripts are used.

The hypothesis is that orthography guides the L2 speaker towards appropriate pronunciation of quantity features in read Swedish speech. The aim of the study is to understand if L2 learners of Swedish with three different L1 backgrounds realize the quantity distinction in stressed syllables and make use of orthographic information. Are there differences that can be related to the speakers' L1 as a phonological and/or orthographic transfer phenomenon?

The results are of interest to get more knowledge about the relation

between orthography and pronunciation in the teaching of Swedish for immigrants.

Background

It is known that L2 learners often transfer linguistic features from their L1 or other languages they master (e.g. Alonso Alonso, 2016). That includes grammar, syntax, lexicon as well as phonology.

In alphabetic scripts there is often no strong one-to-one relation between letters and phonemes or orthography and pronunciation. According to the orthographic depth hypothesis the distance between letter and phoneme differs between languages (Katz & Frost, 1992). In a shallow orthography there is a consistency between letter and phoneme, but in a deep orthography a letter can have more than one sound and one phoneme can be written in different ways. According to Seymour, Aro & Erskine (2003), Finnish and Spanish are two examples of shallow orthographies, while English and French are examples of two deep orthographies, referring. When learning to read and write in a second language a linguistic as well as a metalinguistic competence is of importance (Koda & Zehler, 2008). Therefore, basic knowledge of sentence structure and grammar, symbolic and orthographic knowledge, grapho-morphological and grapho-phonological awareness as well as segmental understanding is necessary.

Consonant length is contrastive in Italian and is shown in the orthography by single and double letters for short and long phonemes respectively (Schmid, 1999). L1 Italian speakers learning English as their L2 produced phonological contrasts between short and long consonants in L2 in a reading task. The duration differences depended on the spelling and was more like the Italian orthography-phoneme system (Bassetti, 2017). The study indicates that the relation between orthography and pronunciation in L1 can be transferred and influence the pronunciation in L2.

Observations in Swedish language L2-classrooms and interviews with teachers in Sweden and Finland indicate that pronunciation instructions do not occur frequently even though teachers mention their importance (Huhtamäki & Zetterholm, 2018). Some of the teachers express that they teach the pronunciation of segments and word stress integrated with lectures on grammar and vocabulary. When following up observations of Swedish L2-lecture, it was revealed that only one teacher mentions the relationship between double spelled consonants and long segments in one class, and that without any further instructions and explanations.

Swedish

In Swedish, the stressed syllable allows a structure, where a long vowel is followed by a short consonant (V:C) or a short vowel is followed by a long consonant (VC:) or a cluster of consonants (Bruce, 2012; Riad, 2014). The complementary quantity contrast in stressed syllables is often shown by single or double consonantal letters in the orthography, *fin* [fi:n] ‘fine’ vs. *finn* [fin:] ‘find’. However, such an orthographic distinction is not always available (e.g. the homograph *man* [ma:n] ‘mane of a horse’ vs. *man* [man:] ‘male human’). It is however safe to assume that double spelling of a consonant brings along a preceding short vowel and a longer consonant, unless there is a morpheme boundary between them.

It should also be pointed out that the primary quantity feature is vowel length, and consonantal length as complement is secondary.

Quantity distinctions of vowels and consonants in stressed syllables appear to be one of the greater difficult prosodic features in L2 learning of Swedish (Bannert, 1990; Zetterholm & Tronnier, 2017). Swedish is classified as a language with a complex syllabic structure and a medium orthographic depth (Seymour et al, 2003).

Albanian

Albanian is comparable to a language with a shallow orthography. The orthography of Albanian allows double spelling of consonants in limited cases. This is not an indication for length, as it refers to a variation in place and manner of articulation of the consonant and to different phonemes. For example <r> and <rr> refer to the phonemes and pronunciation /r/ ([r]) and /r̥/ ([r̥]). One could – of course – argue, that a trill is a long version of a tap. These rhotic contrasts however, can occur in the onset position of a syllable or word, which is not the typical position for quantity distinctions. The difference between <l> and <ll> refer to the phonemes /l/ and /l̥/, and there is no association with any kind of length variation (Krifka, Blaszczyk, Leßmöllman, Meinunger, Stiebels, Tracy & Truckenbrodt, 2014). Double spelling of other consonants does not occur in Albanian. It should be noted that there is a quantity distinction on vowels in the Gheg-dialect (Moosmueller & Granser, 2003), which is not marked in the orthography.

Spanish

Spanish is classified as a language with a simple syllabic structure and a shallow orthography (Seymour et al, 2003). Similarly to Albanian, double spelling of certain consonants occurs in Spanish as well, but does not indicate variation in consonantal or vowel length. The same letters as in Albanian are concerned, namely <r>/<rr> and <l>/<ll> and the pronunciation in Spanish is similar as in Albanian, except for <ll>, which results in a palatal lateral [λ] (Krifka et.al, 2014). Although, <r>/<rr> only occurs in word medial position, this contrast is not considered to account for a quantity distinction in Spanish. In rare cases double spelling <cc> can be found – similarly to English – and the pronunciation is [ks] as in *accidente* ‘accident’. Other consonants are not present as double

spelling, even if this occurs in the original word in Latin: *affectus* (lat.) becomes *afecto* in Spanish (eng. ‘affect’).

Italian

Italian is also classified as a language with a simple syllabic structure and a shallow orthography (Seymour et al, 2003). Consonantal singletons are distinguished from geminates in spelling and production in Italian, e.g. *pala* [ˈpaːla] ‘spade’ vs. *palla* [ˈpaːla] ‘ball’ (Schmid, 1999). Double spelled consonantal letters – i.e. geminates – are produced 1.5-2.5 times as long as the (singleton) counterpart (Pickett, Blumstein & Burton, 1999). Geminata can occur after or before the stressed vowel, i.e. in the coda of a stressed syllable (e.g. *palla* [ˈpaːla] ‘ball’ above) or in the onset, if the stressed syllable is not initial (e.g. *citta* [tʃiˈtːa] ‘city’). Geminata as an assimilatory process can also occur across word or morpheme boundaries. Almost all consonantal phonemes occur as singletons and geminates, that includes voiced and voiceless ones, obstruents, sonorants, rhotics and affricates. A vowel preceding a geminate is known to be produced slightly shorter than a vowel preceding a singleton (Schmid ibd), but variation in consonantal length is primary.

Material and Method

Seven adult L2 learners of Swedish with three different L1 (two Albanian with the Gheg-dialect, two Italian and three Spanish) were recorded when reading sentences with embedded minimal pairs with a quantity distinction. Except for the spelling, the semantic context could be used as a cue for the reader in all sentences. The words in the sentences were all frequently used vernacular words even though not taken from any frequency dictionary (cf. Table 1). All speakers have a good functional command of the Swedish language, acknowledged by either passing standardized tests or by successful use and

comprehension in Swedish-only conversations and situations. For comparison, five native Swedish speakers were recorded reading the same sentences.

The L2 learners studied Swedish for immigrants at different schools. There is no information about if, or how, they were introduced to the relationship between double spelling and vowel and consonant duration respectively.

The vowel and the following consonantal segment in the stressed syllable – which is the initial syllable for all target words – were manually labelled and segmented in PRAAT. Vowel length and the length of the VC-dyad was extracted from the PRAAT-TextGrid. Furthermore, the ratio of the vocalic portion in the VC-dyad was calculated (in percentage [%]). As contrast between short and long consonants and vowels is affected by speech tempo (mainly in Italian (Pickett et al, 1999), but presumably also in other languages), only the values of the ratios are taken into account in the following.

Table 1. Swedish minimal pairs used in the study.

Long vowel	Short vowel
<i>vila</i> (rest) [ˈviːla]	<i>villa</i> (house) [ˈvɪːla]
<i>vägen</i> (the road) [ˈvɛːgən]	<i>väggen</i> (the wall) [ˈvɛgːən]
<i>busar</i> (hooli- gans) [ˈbʊːsar]	<i>bussar</i> (buses) [ˈbʊsːar]

Results

The results are presented in a graphic way in Figure 1 to 3. Each figure presents the results for one of the three word pairs. Hereby, the ratio of the vowel length (in %) in the VC-dyad is given for each speaker: first the results of the five speakers of the Swedish control group, followed by the results of the L2-speakers with the different L1s. The results of the target words, containing long vowels, are displayed by speckled bars and

those of target words containing short vowels are displayed by filled bars.

It is clear from the diagrams, that all speakers of the control group with Swedish as their L1 produce vowels in target words containing phonologically long vowels with a considerably greater vowel ratio—reflecting a longer pronunciation of the vowel—than vowels in target words containing phonologically short vowels. This is the case for all pairs in question. The degree of difference of vowel ratio between the categories varies however somewhat across speakers and word pairs. This can be related to the segmental structure of the word pairs on one hand or to the individual propensity on the other hand.

Figure 1. Vowel ratio (in %) in VC-dyads for the word pair *vila/villa* for all speakers, ordered by their L1.

The results for the Albanian learners of Swedish vary between the two. One speaker (alb1) produces variation of vowel length between the categories in the same way as the Swedish L1-speakers in the control group, i.e. a greater ratio of vowel duration for the phonologically long vowels than for the

phonologically short vowels for each word pair. The other speaker (alb2), however, presents us with rather instable results: for the pairs of words *vila/villa* and *busar/bussar* (Figs. 1 and 3) the vowel ratio is similar between the categories, despite the phonological difference. A difference in ratio is made for the pair *vägen/väggen* (Fig. 2) in the opposite way from what is expected: the vowel in the word *vägen* with a phonologically long vowel was produced with a lower ratio, when compared to the vowel in the word *väggen* with a phonologically short vowel.

Figure 2. Vowel ratio (in %) in VC-dyads for the word pair *vägen/väggen* for all speakers, ordered by their L1.

The Italian learners of Swedish behave in the same way when speaking L2-Swedish as the speakers in the control group. In that way, phonologically long vowels were produced with a greater ratio of duration in the VC-dyad in comparison to the phonologically short vowels for each word pair.

Figure 3. Vowel ratio (in %) in VC-dyads for the word pair *busar/bussar* for all speakers, ordered by their L1.

In the case of Spanish learners of Swedish, spa1 and spa3 hardly make any differences between phonologically long and short vowels for the word pairs *vägen/väggen* and *busar/bussar* (Figs 2 and 3). Furthermore, the minimal observable difference is in reverse to what should be the case, i.e., the wrong word in the pairs receives a slightly greater ratio. Speaker2 (spa2) on the other hand, produces slightly greater ratios for the vowels in the expected words in all pairs, the difference in vowel ratio between the words in each pair is, however, not as large as for the L1-speakers in the Swedish control group. All speakers distinguish between long and short vowels for the pair *vila/villa* in the appropriate way (Fig. 1). For the speakers spa1 and spa3, this distinction is only marginal, whereas speaker spa3 presents us with a difference in vowel ratio between the word pairs to an extent, which is similar to the results of the L1-speakers in the Swedish control group.

Discussion and conclusions

Double spelled consonants seem to be a good orthographic cue for quantity distinctions in Swedish for the Italian learners, as similar orthographic cues occur in Italian. This is in accordance with the study by Bassetti (2017) about Italian learners' pronunciation of English. Although double spelling of consonants does occur in both Albanian and Spanish, it is not related to any quantity distinction and therefore, a comparable transfer advantage is probably not available for those learners of Swedish. As seen in Fig 1 to 3 there is also individual variation between speakers. Unfortunately, we have no specific information about the learners' education in Swedish.

The results raise questions about the teaching of Swedish and how such an orthographic cue is highlighted in the second language classroom, as quantity distinctions is vital in Swedish. Teachers are recommended to make the learners aware of those orthographic cues. This is primarily important for learners with L1s, where no quantity distinctions occur and double spelling signals other pronunciation characteristics.

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References

- Alonso Alonso, R. (ed.) (2016). *Crosslinguistic Influence in Second Language Acquisition*. Bristol; Buffalo: Multilingual Matters.
- Bannert, R. (1990). *På väg mot svenskt uttal*. Lund: Studentlitteratur.
- Bassetti, B. (2008). Orthographic input and second language phonology. In: T. Piske & M. Young-Scholten (eds.) *Input matters in SLA*. Clevedon: UK: Multilingual matters, 191–206.
- Bassetti, B. (2017). Orthography affect second language speech: Double letters

- and geminate production in *English. Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning, Memory, and Cognition* 2017, Vol.43, No.11, 1835–1842.
- Bassetti, B., Escudero, Pl. & Hayes-Harb, R. (2015). Second language phonology at the interface between acoustic and orthographic input. *Applied Psycholinguistics*, 36, 1–6.
- Bruce, G. (2012). *Svensk och allmän prosodi*. Lund: Studentlitteratur.
- Huhtamäki, M. & Zetterholm, E. (2018). Uttalets plats i undervisningen i svenska som andraspråk. *AFinLA-E: Soveltavan Kielitieteen Tutkimuksia*, (10), 45–60. <https://doi.org/10.30660/afinla.73123>.
- Katz, L. & Frost, R. (1992). The Reading Process is Different for Different Orthographies: The Orthographic Depth Hypothesis. *Haskins Laboratories Status Report on Speech Research*, SR-111/112, 147–160.
- Koda, K. & Zehler, A.M. (2008). *Learning to Read Across Languages: Cross-Linguistic Relationships in First- and Second Language Literacy Development*. Taylor and Francis.
- Krifka, M., Błaszczak, J., Leßmöllmann, A., Meinunger, A., Stiebels, B., Tracy, R. & Truckenbrodt, H. (eds) (2014). *Das mehrsprachige Klassenzimmer. Über die Muttersprachen unserer Schüler*. Springer-Verlag Berlin-Heidelberg.
- Moosmueller, S. & Granser, T. (2003). The vowels of Standard Albanian *Proc. 15th Int. Congress of Phonetic Sciences (ICPhS2003)*, Barcelona, pp. 659–662.
- Pickett, E., Blumstein, S. & Burton, M.W. (1999). Effects of speaking rate on the singleton/geminate consonant contrast in Italian. *Phonetica* 56. 135–157.
- PRAAT, <http://www.fon.hum.uva.nl/praat/>.
- Riad, T. (2014). *The Phonology of Swedish*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Schmid, S. (1999). *Fonetica e fonologia dell'italiano*. Turin: Paravia scriptorium.
- Seymour, P.H.K., Aro, M. & Erskine, J.M. (2003). Foundation literacy acquisition in European orthographies. *British Journal of Psychology*, 94, 143–174.
- Vogel, I. (1982). *La sillaba come unità fonologica*. Bologna: Zanichelli.
- Zetterholm, E. & Tronnier, M. (2017). *Perspektiv på svenskt uttal. Fonologi, brytning och didaktik*. Lund: Studentlitteratur.